

1. JOINING TECHNOLOGIES COMBINING CFRPS AND 3D METAL ANCHORS FOR AERONAUTICAL STRUCTURAL PARTS: CASE STUDY- VERTICAL STABILIZER

Evanthia Pappa*¹, Federico Danzi¹, Abhishek Kumar¹, , Angelico Campilungo¹, Ciro Annicchiarico², Sportelli Angelo², Mattia Cabrioli^{3,4}, María Silva Colmenero^{3,4}, Matteo Vanazzi^{3,4}, Boris Fošnarič⁵, Tina Černelič⁵, Valter Capitani⁶, Stefano Pasquino⁶, Luca Margaria⁷, Enes F. Altunok⁷, Antonio Coluccia⁷, Giorgio De Pasquale⁷

¹ Leonardo s.p.a., Quantum Technologies, Optronics & Material Laboratories, Leonardo Innovation Hub, Italy

² Leonardo s.p.a., Leonardo Aerostructures Division, Italy

³ f3nice, Gaustadalléen 21, 0349 Oslo, Norway

⁴ f3nice, Via Roccoli, 252, 23010 Piantedo, SO, Italy

⁵VEPLAS d.d., Cesta Simona Blatnika 11, 3320 Velenje, Slovenia

⁶TUV Italia srl TUV Group, Turin, PI, Italy

⁷Politecnico di Torino, Smart Structures and Systems Lab, Italy

*Corresponding author: evanthia.pappa@leonardo.com

ABSTRACT

Composites were initially employed in aerospace for non-critical applications. However, in recent decades, their use has expanded to primary structures, such as fuselages. The integration of diverse materials in aircraft structures presents a significant challenge in terms of joining techniques. The advancement of joining technologies for composite materials remains a critical area of research and engineering. In aerospace applications, the reliance on adhesives, fasteners, and rivets is often associated with high costs, extended manufacturing times, and potential performance limitations, necessitating the development of more efficient and cost-effective solutions. The EU-funded MIMOSA project develops a new innovative process based on multi-material joining of Additively Manufactured of AlSi10Mg and CFRP components. To demonstrate their use in aeronautical applications, a primary structure was selected as a case study. Vertical stabilizers provide the stability and the aircraft control during flight conditions while being subjected to various loads. Assessing of torsional and bending loads is essential for the structural analysis of such parts while taking into consideration the following factors: weight, material strength and stability. In this case study, the performance of new joining technologies is assessed by manufacturing and testing a scaled-down vertical stabilizer and the technology is validated by developing a business model.

2. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials present widespread applications for more than 50 including, automotive, renewable energy, aerospace, aeronautics, healthcare, etc. In aviation in particular, the use of composite materials exploded in from mid-90 up onwards, and it is projected to be even higher the following years. The latest trend in aerospace community is the exploration of hybrid composite to reduce the use of traditional bonding technologies such as mechanical or adhesive bonding; which add more weight and manufacturing defects to the structure, i.e. poor

compatibility, local damages of the laminate structure. Hybrid composites is the term that is used for joining dissimilar materials. Among the first developments in form fit elements (also known as z-pins) is CMT pins urfi-Sculp structures made of titanium [2], HYPER pins made of aluminium [3]. There are also studies using weldable inserts [4, 8] and through additive manufacturing (AM) [9-12].

AM has been recently integrated into part production for the aerospace sector, to leverage on cost and lead time reduction, in combination with increased capability to produce parts with unconventional and complex design [13] Additionally, AM of aluminium alloys was extensively studied, to understand the trade-off between the beneficial effects of AM production and potential risks given by intrinsic typical defects generated into printed parts [14]. Since AlSi10Mg is one of the most widespread materials for AM applications, especially for the automotive and aerospace sector, comprehensive knowledge has been developed on the output of various AM techniques in terms of part quality and performance. In particular, considering Powder Bed Fusion with Laser Beam (LB-PBF), the correlation between microstructure and mechanical performance is well known. Hence by fine tuning the process parameters and post-processing phases such as heat treatment, it is possible to target specific performances for the manufactured parts [15]. Moreover, considering specifically innovative joining technologies for dissimilar materials, the role of surface quality of metal parts assumes higher importance. In particular, effects of surface defects on fatigue life and the use of novel finishing techniques to improve the lifetime of small-scale components were recently investigated [16].

For these reasons, AM appears to be the most promising technique to produce metal parts for hybrid composites, as it involves low-cost-fast-production while decreasing the use of scrap materials and the overall carbon footprint. A review by Kellar et al [1], presented a concise report identifying 7 distinct strategies for joining fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) to metals, Figure 1. The authors are addressing the challenges of joining composites with metals emphasizing the manufacturing challenges, the initial increased costs, quality uncertainty and the evident resistance to adaptation of new technologies; especially in aviation.

Figure 1. Summarised approaches for joining hybrid composites [1]

New designs or material modifications of existing structures require to undergo a safety and performance validation for their certification. MIMOSA's ambitious concept is the development of a multi-material join for the coupling of CFRP and the metal parts for primary aircraft structure avoiding the use of rivets. Additional developments of MIMOSA were

published in [6, 7, 18-19]. The project is divided in three main pillars; i) the development of the AlSi10Mg metal designs with additive manufacturing (AM), ii) the optimization of the surface and the bonding strategy of the CFRP laminates to the metal part and iii) the recycling of the hybrid composite and the up-cycling of the metal powder.

Market analysis

Aerospace and Defence (A&D) industries are experiencing a significant recovery from the pandemic with projected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of almost 14%. Due to the

high demand, the focus is on strategic expansion to technologies with increased production rate, controlled supply chain and increased performance. Additive manufacturing is projected to a revenue of approx. \$ 88.3 billion by 2030 globally with the highest share hold by A&D sector. Focusing on the metal additive manufacturing, there is a great increase of more than 28% in CAGR with the metal 3D printing being the fastest development sector with expected revenues of \$ 35.32 billion by 2030. The aforementioned increased trend has

a direct linked to the increased metal powder market with a CAGR of almost 10% until 2027. Europe, and more specifically Spain, is leading the metal powder market. The later includes all metal types, such as Titanium, Aluminium, Steel and other alloys. Similarly, advanced composite materials is expected to reach almost \$75.0 billion by 2030. Asia and Pacific is projected as the largest market but U.S. has the highest growing rate of almost 8.5% annually. In Europe Germany is leading the advanced composites industry with the faster growing segment being the carbon fibres. The extensive use of both metals and composites along with the blueprint of the sustainable development; a similar trend on recycling processed is foreseen for the same forecasting period.

Figure 2: Market size from 2023 projected to 2030 for the main technologies of MIMOSA Project; Metal AM, Power Metal, Advanced Composites and Additive manufacturing.

Metal recycling is a sector that is already well-established and is expected to have a ca. 7% CAGR by 2030 while composite recycling is still under development and is projected with almost half CAGR. Composite recycling technologies can be categorized into 3 main segments a. mechanical recycling, b. incineration/co-incineration and c. chemical decomposition (such as solvolysis); all of which have their own limitations for scaling up. On the other hand, metal recycling can be conducted by following two main pathways. The first one involves the releting of scrap metal, taking care of controlling the chemical composition of input and output

metal in order to improve the quality of the alloys (upcycling), rather than maintaining grade or leaving impurities in the melt (down-cycling). Therefore, ingots are produced for further refining or production processes. On the other hand, an alternative and innovative recycling path consists in the collection of selected scrap metal, to be able to maintain the grade of chosen metal alloys or even upcycle them, for the production of feedstock for AM, namely in the form of atomized powders or wires. In this way, it would be possible to implement closed loop strategies for recycling, which can improve the global trading limitations and improve the EU supply chain resilience.

Case Study

Hybrid composites are getting more and more attention in transportation applications, i.e. aviation, due to reduced fuel consumption. The vertical stabilizer (VS), as part of aircraft, is the static part of the vertical tail. It is composed by a fixed surface and one or more hinged movable rudders; providing control, stability and trim in yaw. The prototype of the VS is a scaled down design of an Airbus A220 consisting of a CFRP skin and aluminium alloys fittings.

Figure 3: Case study: Vertical stabilizer

The research content of MIMOSA Project involves the development of a method to eliminate the use of rivets and adhesions for the bonding of the vertical stabilizer to the fuselage. The proposed joint replacing traditional riveting with a novel lattice layer that optimizes differences in thermal expansion and surface anchors designed to promote interlocking with the CFRP composite, figure 4.

MIMOSA

Figure 4: MIMOSA's joining technology

The prototype was manufactured and tested under static loading. End-of-life processes were used for the recycling of all the tested coupons as well as the recycling and reclamation of the metal powders; resulting on a closed loop sustainable business case.

3. RESEARCH TESTS & EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Materials

The materials that were used for the manufacturing of the demonstrator were selected based on their mechanical and physical performance. A standard aviation toughened grade CFRP prepreg (CYCOM 977-2) was supplied by [Syensqo](#) for the manufacturing of the composite part. Commercial powders obtained by gas atomization (EOS Aluminium AlSi10Mg) and supplied by [EOS](#) constituted the feedstock for AM production of the metal side of the joints.

3.2 Manufacturing

Additive manufacturing was used to produce metal parts of AlSi10Mg with optimized topology and surface anchors promoting the effect of interlocking. Preparatory studies led to identification of suitable process parameters related to the LB-PBF process on an EOS M290 printed. Consequently, mechanical performance under static and dynamic loads were assessed on different scales, to ensure reliability of the components both in bulk regions and surface anchors [17]. Optimized process parameters [20, 21] were applied to manufacture three fittings, with different designs compatible with the above-mentioned vertical stabilizer.

The metal parts were coated with atmospheric-pressure plasma deposition for corrosion resistance and better adhesion to the composite. The joining technology occurred with the co-curing of the composite with the metal anchors following a debagging process to increase the compaction of the laminates to the metal anchors. The parts were cured in an autoclave following the standard curing process suggested by the supplier. The demonstrators were inspected with non-disruptive testing (ultrasonication) to verify the quality of demo.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Numerical Analysis

The numerical investigation focused on the stress distribution in the fitting when using a 15 mm thick support plate in steel with a combined bolted and adhesive connection. In this configuration, the interface between the fitting and plate was modelled with both frictional contact (to represent the bolted connection) and increased contact stiffness to reflect the lap shear strength of the structural adhesive. The simulation setup included a bolt pretension of 20,000 N per M8 bolt, a distributed load of 225,000 N applied to the fitting-CFRP joining surface at an angle of 38.89° to the global XY plane and 6.51° to the global XZ plane, and fixed boundary conditions at both ends of the pin, allowing rotation about its axis.

The results, illustrated in Figure 5, show the equivalent (von Mises) stress contours across the assembly for the 15 mm plate case. High stress concentrations are observed around the fitting-pin interface, with localized values exceeding the failure threshold for AlSi10Mg, indicated by the red regions in the contour plot. A sectional view through the fitting-pin region (Figure 5) provides further detail, where three stress probes were placed to quantify the local stress values. The probe data confirm that the critical stress concentrations are not substantially mitigated by the addition of adhesive to the bolted connection for this plate thickness.

Section View Stress Probe Values [MPa]	
Probe1	383.59
Probe2	496.89
Probe3	437.48
Average	439.32

Figure 5 Von Mises stress distribution at the pin.

Overall, the simulation demonstrates that, for the 15 mm plate with bolted/adhesive interface, the critical stress distribution in the fitting remains largely unchanged compared to other configurations. The persistent high-stress zones near the pin connection suggest that further design modifications, beyond adhesive addition or plate thickness increase, are necessary to effectively reduce peak stresses in this critical region.

4.2 Experimental Analysis

All fittings were tested under tension until failure. Tensile tests were performed on an MTS universal frame under crosshead displacement control (0.5 mm/min) with a loading cell of 300kN. To simulate bolt-bearing in an aircraft structure, a custom steel jig was designed, figure 6A. The jig clamps the composite panel edges while a hardened stainless shaft—acting as a bolt—passes through the fitting hole, loading the aluminium in pure bearing. The experimental procedure was based on an early study [22, 23] on the critical loading conditions of the VS, Figure 6B. Fitting 1 represents the forward fitting (FWD), fitting 2 represents the middle fitting (MID) and fitting 3 represents the rear fitting (REAR).

Figure 6 Example of the set up. A) Bolt-bearing simulation (left); experimental (right) and B) fluid dynamics force reaction results of each fitting.

In this document only the results of fitting 1 will be discussed. The fitting failed in the aluminium open-hole junction area, following a plastic deformation and a rupture, figure 7. The open-hole diameter elongated in the direction of the load and shortened in the opposite direction. During static loading there were significant changes in the dislocations within the material, including variations in their distribution, quantity, and morphology; resulting in prolonged elongation. Earlier studies [24] are discussing the microstructure of the heat-treated AlSi10Mg material and provide enough evidence to conclude that micro-meter size second-phase particles have low efficiency in hindering dislocation motion, thereby enhancing dislocation mobility and facilitating their directional alignment resulting in elongation and rupture. The dimensions of the fitting 1 in the junction area was thickness ~15mm and diameter ~21mm. Comparative c-scan imaging was obtained through ultrasonic inspection prior and after the static test of fitting 1 carbon-metal region of the joints. The images reveal regions with varying shades of grey, corresponding to differences in ultrasonic signal attenuation as it propagates through the sample material. Specifically, darker areas, indicative of higher signal attenuation, are typically associated with the presence of an adhesion interface between carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) and metal. Conversely, lighter regions suggest lower attenuation, often correlated with poor adhesion or even a lack of contact between CFRP and metal. In the analysed samples, excluding the lighter lateral regions — attributable to the exclusive presence of CFRP — the carbon-metal interface zones exhibit a regular pattern of

grey-level variations. This distribution is interpreted as indicative of differing adhesion levels between the materials, particularly in the pin regions, both at the upper extremities and in the inter-pin areas. The fitting 1, resulted with new high-intensity signal areas (panels D and E, red, green, and yellow zones) which indicate interfacial changes. By analysing the depth of the indicated regions relative to the laminate thickness, the presence of internal delamination within the solid composite can be excluded. Therefore, the observed variations are attributed to a reduction in adhesion quality or a loss of contact between CFRP and metal, rather than to damage within the laminate itself.

Figure 7 Stress-strain curves of all fittings, c-scans and rapture representation

Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique was employed to capture the full strain field of the joints throughout the entire loading process. Images were acquired using a Basler a2A4096-30umPRO camera with 12 MPx resolution, equipped with a 12 mm fixed Fujinon lens. The recordings were taken at a frame rate of 0.5 Hz, with the camera positioned 160 mm from the specimen and a pixel to mm ratio of 0.044 Px/mm. The region under the lag was selected as region of interest to identify possible disbanding of the anchors from the composite substrate. Fig. 8a shows, in blue, the selected Region Of Interest (ROI) in the initial phase of the test together with three longitudinal virtual extensometers aligned with the loading direction and positioned in the transition zone of the connection and the central one aligned with the lug connection. The analysis were carried out using the MatchID software using a subset size of

41 Px with a step size of 20 Px; the ANSSD algorithm has been adopted as correlation criterion while quadratic shape function has been used to reconstruct the strain field. Eventually the strain field has been calculated via quadratic interpolation function. The results of the virtual strain gauges, Fig. 8b, highlighted after an initial adjustment phase, a linear elastic response of the joint followed by the progressive non-linear deformation during the plasticization of the lug. Both the vertical displacement and strain field at the transition peak of the elastic region are shown in Fig.9a and b. While the displacement field shows a clear vertical movement of the lug (the negative values are due to the reference system here considered) that degrades toward the bottom part of the ROI the strain field does not show any indication of possible anchor deteriorations; minor fluctuations have been attributed to the speckle quality.

Figure 8 (a) Region of interest for Fitting 1, (b) Virtual strain gauges elongation.

Figure 9(a) Vertical displacement field, (b) Vertical strain field.

Figure 10 Test procedure of the VS (Fitting 1).

Overall, and based on the results presented, the interlocking behaviour is present and relevant resistant to the applied forces. The damage in the joints is neglected as a) in DIC results no localised jump was observed in that region and b) from the c-scan comparison before and after the static loading the area of interest present very little damage towards the edge of the joints. Hence, it can be concluded that the joints performed well under the margins for fitting 1 enhancing the indicators for a positive uptake of the technology and its potential to aeronautical primary structures.

Last but not least, to perform a conclusive study, the business canvas related to the business model of MIMOSA Project is being defined taking into account the current market trends and the strategic pathways towards new technological advancements. The business canvas identifies, key activities related to the business case of MIMOSA Project, the key partnerships and relationships (stakeholders, customers, policy makers, etc) that can be built, the breakdown of the cost requirements and other general key aspects of a successful business case.

Figure 11 MIMOSA's Business Canvas.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents an innovative, rivet-free joining technology incorporating additive manufactured AlSi10Mg metal fittings and CFRP laminates as part of an aeronautical primary structure. Experimental and numerical analysis conclude that the interlocking design increases the performance of the joint when compared to common rivet practices aligning with aerospace safety requirements and sustainability goals in aviation by using closed-looped practices. MIMOSA's findings can open new perspectives in the market of joints with certified strategies, cost-effective and sustainable solutions for the future use in aviation.

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